

ETHNIC CLEANSING OF PALESTINIANS - ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW IN PROTECTING CIVILIANS.

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ABSTRACT

Today's human rights violations are the causes of tomorrow's conflicts, as rightly said by Mary Robinson. International humanitarian laws are praised more than ever and violated as much as ever. Ethnic cleansing and genocides, a systematic approach to remove religious groups are no doubt, the most common and severe of the crimes against human beings under the International Humanitarian Law and its failure to safeguard the victims is dreadful which in turn has led to this increased number of genocides we are encountering even in the modern era. The beginning of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict dates back to the 19th and early 20th century when Zionism was established as a political ideology and continues to have its existence to this very day. This research aims to bring the historical background and political aspects of the issue to light so the next time acts of barbarity of this nature are repeated we will have archival data to support the truth and existence of a place called Palestine. It examines the role of International Humanitarian Law and questions the very foundation of its actor in protecting the rights of the civilians and how it has atrociously failed in doing so. In this study the researcher has adopted the Library-based, Analytical and Mixed Method (Qualitative and Quantitative approach) to evaluate the part played by the codified laws in protecting the victims including a large number of women and children. This research shall provide a way forward, an analysis of violation of rights and legitimate ways of action that should be taken into consideration in order to eradicate inaction and protect the civilians because the conflict on which the study is based, ought to be repeated as long as actions are taken in the manner in which they have presently been taken.

Keywords- Ethnic Cleansing, International Humanitarian Law, Palestinians, Genocide, Human Rights Violation

“Every Second I am dying inside, for Ukraine. I'm dying for Afghanistan, I'm dying for Palestine, I'm dying Kashmir. Even my pen pours blood. And this bleeding won't stop till I put an end to the bloodshed of innocents”

- Abhijit Naskar, The Gentalist : There's No Social Work, Only Family Work

Chapter 1-

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND OF THE ROOT CAUSE-

The origin of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict almost went back to 2000 years ago. In 1897, some Jews living in Europe founded the *World Zionist Organisation* at Basley, in Switzerland. Zionists were the people who believed that Jews ought to be able to go back to Palestine and have what they called for a national homeland in Palestine. After the Jews had recently suffered persecution in Russia, France and Germany, and a Jewish state would provide a safe refuge for them from all over the world. Palestine was already inhabited by the Arabs who were understandably alarmed at the prospect of losing their land to the Jews.

It was in the year 1917 when Britain got involved, after the Foreign Minister, Arthur Balfour announced that they supported the idea of a Jewish national home in Palestine. After 1919, when Palestine was made a British Mandate, large number of Jews began to arrive in Palestine, and the Arabs protested bitterly to the British that they wanted an independent Palestine for themselves and an end to the immigration of Jews. ***The Arabs were persuaded that the British government had no intention to occupy the whole of Palestine and that there would be no interference with the rights of the Palestinian Arabs.*** It was clearly shown in the declaration of Balfour where he made a statement promising *‘nothing shall be done which may prejudice the civil and religious rights of the existing non-Jewish communities in Palestine’*

Through all this persuasion, the British hoped to encourage the Jews and the Arabs to live together peacefully in the same state yet failed miserably to understand the deep religious gulf between the two and hence the Balfour's promise turned out to be a failure.

The failure of the British Mandate to honour the assurances given to the Arab population had far-reaching demographic consequences. By 1948, the first Arab-Israeli war resulted in the forced

displacement of approximately 750,000 Palestinians, representing roughly two-thirds of the total Arab population, in an event Palestinians refer to as the *Nakba*, meaning “catastrophe”.¹ More than 400 Palestinian villages were systematically depopulated or destroyed in the period between 1948 and 1950, and today the registered Palestinian refugee population and their descendants number in excess of 5.8 million persons, constituting one of the world’s largest and most protracted refugee crises.

It was further in the year of 1933, that the Nazi persecution of Jews in Germany caused a flood of refugees and by 1940 about half of the population of Palestine was Jewish. Violent protest by the Arabs and an uprising which the British tried to suppress with brutality killing over 3000 Arabs started in the year 1936. Palestine was divided into two separate states by the *British Peel Commission in 1937*; one Arab and one Jewish but the Arabs rejected this idea.

What made the situation worse?

It was the *Second World War* that worsened the situation where hundreds of thousands of Jewish refugees from Hitler’s Europe desperately looking for some way to go found their way to Palestine. In 1945, the USA pressed to allow 100000 Jews into Palestine, and the demand was echoed by David Ben Gurion, a Jewish leader and this demand was straightforwardly refused by the British. It was after this the Jewish started a terrorist campaign against both the Arabs and the British; which led to one of the most spectacular incidents of blowing up the King David Hotel in Jerusalem, which the Britishers were using as their headquarters. The British response to this was the arrest of the Jewish leaders and turning back of the ship such as *Exodus*, crammed with Jews intending to enter Palestine.

Weakened by the strain of the *Second World War*, British felt unable to cope with the Labour Foreign Secretary and asked the United Nations to step in and deal with the problem which led to the division of Palestine setting aside roughly half of it to form an independent Jewish State, by

¹ Institute for Middle East Understanding, ‘Quick Facts: The Palestinian Nakba (Catastrophe)’ (IMEU) <<https://imeu.org/resources/resources/quick-facts-the-palestinian-nakba-catastrophe/142>> accessed 10 June 2025.

the UN vote in 1947. This incident led the outburst of various wars such the Suez War of 1956 and the Six Day War of 1967.

Peace between Israel and the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO)-

During the year 1992 the election of a less aggressive government in Israel reached home for better relations with the Palestinians. A major breakthrough, took place at the conference in Oslo, and became known as the Oslo accords. This peace Accord of September 1993 made agreements such as-

Israel formally recognized the PLO.

The PLO recognized Israel's right to exist and promised to give up terrorism.

The Palestinians were to be given limited self-rule in Jericho (on the West Bank) and in part of the Gaza Strip, areas occupied by Israel since the 1967 war. And Israeli troops would be withdrawn from these areas. However, the extremist groups from both the sides opposed to the agreement.

The problem of Jerusalem-

The Oslo Accords had by-passed several vital questions, such as the status of Jerusalem, the right of return of the 1948 refugees, and the future of the Jewish settlements in the areas occupied by Israel since 1967.

The original UN intention after the creation of Israel was that the Jerusalem should be under the International control. But that was not so and East of Jerusalem was captured by the Israel until the Six-day War along with the entire West Bank from Jordan which is still occupied by the Israelis even today. The problem that exists is that Jerusalem as a great symbolic and emotional significance for both the sides. For the Jews, it was their ancient capital city and they believe the Temple Mount was the site of their temple in biblical times. And for the Palestinians, Jerusalem known as *Al Haram al-Sharif* is the site from which the Prophet Muhammad ascended into heaven. That is really is worse so determined to hold on to Jerusalem that it took over the land from the Arab and built new settlements, completely in violation of international law.

CHAPTER 2-

LITERATURE REVIEW-

2.1 Report

Amnesty International-

This is a historic vindication of the rights of Palestinians have endured the kinds of cruelty and systematic human rights violation stemming from Israel's unlawful occupation.

The occupation is a key pillar of the system of apartheid that Israel uses to dominate and suppress Palestinians, and which has caused suffering on a mass scale. They have witnessed their homes being demolished, the lands expropriated to build and expand settlements, and have faced suffocating restrictions disrupting every aspect of their daily lives from restrictions on freedom to denial of access to land water and natural resources.

The international community, in particular Israel's allies, must now take unequivocal action to ensure Israel ends its unlawful occupation, starting with the immediate halting of the expansion of Israeli settlement and reversing the annexation of Palestinian territory, including East Jerusalem, and dismantling its brutal system of apartheid against Palestinians. Ending the occupation is crucial in order to stop the recurrent pattern of human rights. Violations across Israel and the Occupied Palestinian Territories.

After the long-awaited advisory opinion which stated the Israel's occupation as a clear violation of international law, in July 2004, the International Court of Justice issued its first advisory opinion finding that the construction of the separation wall inside the Occupied Palestinian Territories had to be halted because it was contrary to International Law. The International community's failure to implement the recommendations of the 2004 ICJ opinion has emboldened Israel's defiance of international law and reinforced its impunity²

² Amnesty International, 'ICJ Opinion Declaring Israel's Occupation of Palestinian Territories Unlawful Is Historic Vindication of Palestinians'

2.2 Books

Book- Mastering Modern World History by Norman Lowe.

This book is about world history dealing with topics such War and International Relations and Global Problems. One such chapter consists of the summary of events of Conflicts in the Middle East and the creation of Israel and the Arab- Israel War, 1948-9, is one of the many topics. Certain extracts from the book have been quoted for reference-

‘The war and its outcome-

Most people expected the Arabs to win easily, but against seemingly overwhelming odds, that is Riley is defeated them and even captured more of Palestine than the UN partition had given them. They ended up with about three- quarters of Palestine plus the Egyptian port of Eilat on the Red Sea. The Israel is one as many of the troops had again military experience fighting in the British army during the second world war. The Arab states were divided among themselves and poorly equipped. The Palestinians themselves were demoralized, and their military organisation had been destroyed by the British during the uprisings of 1936-9. —

The most tragic outcome of the war was that the Palestinian Arabs became the innocent victims: they had suddenly lost 3/4 of their homeland, and the majority were now without a state of their

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Rights’ (28 July 2024) <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2024/07/icj-opinion-declaring-israels-occupation-of-palestinian-territories-unlawful-is-historic-vindication-of-palestinians-rights/>

<<https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2024/07/icj-opinion-declaring-israels-occupation-of-palestinian-territories-unlawful-is-historic-vindication-of-palestinians-rights/>> accessed 28 December 2024.

own. Somewhere in the new Jewish state of Israel; others found themselves living in the area known as the West Bank occupied by Jordan.’³

Book-Historical roots of Palestinian Problem by Maulana Syed Abul A’la Maududi

This book has a detailed historical background and perspective of the Palestinian Conflict, beginning from how the Jews planned it all, how the First World War and Balfour Declaration is related to the problem, what was the role of League of Nations, the dubious part played by the British Mandate. The concept of National Home to National State by the time United Nations decided to enforce a ceasefire in November 1948, a little over 77% of the Palestine was under Jewish occupation has been explained briefly. With all this, explanation of the various phases of the British Plan has also been cited in the book.⁴

Book- A Study of History by Arnold J Toynbee-

Toynbee, the renowned historian, writes in his book “They (the acts) were no less cruel than those committed by Hitler on Jews themselves”

2.3 Articles

Article -Occupation is the Atrocity by Professor Edward Said

³ Norman Lowe, *Mastering Modern World History* 230–231 (5th edn, Palgrave Macmillan 2013).

⁴ Syed Abul A’la Maududi, *Historical Roots of Palestinian Problem* 18–22 (Markazi Maktaba Islami Publishers 2017).

Edward Wadie Said was a Palestinian-American academic, literary critic and political activist. In this article, Occupation is the Atrocity, he has commented on the plight of the Palestinians and the atrocious highhandedness of Israel, certain paragraphs of the article have been quoted:

“The appallingly unbroken history of Israel's 34-year-old military occupation (the second longest in modern history) of illegally concurred Palestinian land has been obliterated from public memory nearly everywhere, as has been the destruction of Palestinian Society in 1948 and the expulsion of 68% of its native people, of whom 4.5 million remain refugees today.

Behind the reins of new speak, the stark outlines of Israel's decades long daily pressure on a people who is means in is that they happened to be there, in Israel is way, is staggeringly perceptible in its inhuman sadism. The fantastically cruel confinement of 1.3 million people jammed like so many humans are dimes into the Gaza Strip, plus the newly 2 million Palestinian residents of the west bank, has no parallel in the annals of the apartheid or colonialism.

Israel's plan is not just to hold land and fill it with dreadful murderers I am settlers who, defended by the Army, wreak havoc and Palestinian orchards, schoolchildren and homes; it is, as the American researcher Sara Roy has named it, to de develop Palestinian Society, to make life impossible so that the Palestinians will leave, or give up somehow, or do something crazy like blow themselves up.”⁵

Chapter 3-

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY-

This chapter outlines the Statement of Problem, Rationale, Methodology used, Research Questions and its Objective.

Statement of the Problem-

⁵ Edward W Said, ‘Occupation Is the Atrocity’ (Al-Ahram Weekly, 2000).

This research shall outline the violation of rights of the people of Palestine majorly including women and children, how the actors of International Humanitarian Law failed to protect them from so long, the most recent being started from the year 2023 and what implication, complexities and standard it has set up.

Rationale of the research-

The rationale behind our research is to not let this history get lost in the high-tech modern era where everything is in our fingertips today and denied or lost later, our aim is to protect this piece of information in the form of archival data in our modern world history.

Research Questions-

1. How the International Humanitarian law has neglected the grave violation and failed?
2. Why was no *Suo moto cognizance* taken and why was there unusual delay leading to inaction? What steps has the International Court of Justice taken during the period of October 2023- October 2024.
3. What is the role of United Nations Organisations?
4. Were the Palestinian women and children protected?

Research methodology-

The researchers have adopted Analytical and the Mixed Method (Qualitative and Quantitative approach) for the outcome of this study. The research design is framed by literature review. The framework of this research includes some authentic websites, notable reports and books.

Chapter-4

ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW AND ITS ACTORS

In the words of **Oppenheim**, *International law previously known as Law of Nations is simply the name for the body of customary rules and treaties which are considered legally binding upon by the states in their intercourse with each other.* The analytical jurist, **Holland** remarks that *international law can indeed be described as law only by courtesy, since the rights with which it*

is concerned cannot properly be described as legal. If we look at the term International Humanitarian law, it is of relatively recent origin and a branch of it is International Law which provides protection to human beings. The origin of this law can be traced back to the *Geneva conventions, 1849 and Hague Conventions of 1899 and 1907*. The pivotal role of International humanitarian law is to protect human life during armed conflict and situations of violence. Rules of international humanitarian law are inspired by the principles of humanity and they are meant to avoid the human suffering, barbarism and brutality.

Notwithstanding the comprehensiveness of these codified protections, scholars and practitioners have consistently noted a persistent gap between the normative framework of IHL and its effective implementation in practice. The International Committee of the Red Cross, in its 2024 report on the challenges of contemporary armed conflict, observed that the absence of political will to enforce existing norms, rather than any deficiency in the rules themselves, remains the principal cause of civilian suffering in armed conflicts.⁶ The Common Article 1 obligation upon all High Contracting Parties to “respect and ensure respect” for the Geneva Conventions in all circumstances has thus far failed to produce meaningful enforcement action against states that have carried out documented violations in the Occupied Palestinian Territory.

Geneva convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Times of War, 1949-

If we take a closer look at this convention, it mentions that all parties to the conflict are bound by **Article 3 of the 1949 Convention**, which establishes a minimum standard to be followed and demands humane treatment of all people.

In the Nicaragua case⁷, the international Court of Justice has observed that the principles of humanitarian law or identical with the elementary consideration of humanity. Another aspect raises the question as to whether human rights or legal rights? *Para 2 of Article 2 of Declaration of*

⁶ ICRC, ‘International Humanitarian Law and the Challenges of Contemporary Armed Conflicts’ (2024) International Review of the Red Cross <<https://international-review.icrc.org/articles/reports-and-documents-ihl-and-the-challenges-of-contemporary-armed-conflicts-927>> accessed 10 June 2025.

⁷ *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v United States of America)* (Merits) [1986] ICJ Rep 14 [218].

Human Rights mention that each state shall adopt necessary legislative and administrative steps to ensure that the right to protect human rights is effectively guaranteed along with various other Covenants such as International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, it is implied that human right is a legal right. While human beings have rights, the state has a corresponding duty to protect it. This study portrays how actors such as **Universal Declaration of human Rights, International Covenants on Human Rights, Regional Conventions, Internatioanl Court of Justice, CEDAW** has played in the genocide in question.

If we look at how the International Humanitarian law has neglected the grave violation and failed, the answer is very well shown through the numerical data and demographic status of death rates which is up to an approximation of 3% per 1000 inhabitants. The portrayal of deaths and destruction has been seen by all of us through the expansion and popularization of social media. When we see death, the system is supposed to get out of their administrative cocoon to take on ground actions which was neglected by the international humanitarian law. Here the remarks of the analytical jurist, *Holland*, is very well suited that '*International law can indeed be described as law only by courtesy*', because we have seen the lack of compliance and sanction.

Moving towards the role of International Court of Justice in the duration of October 2023 to October 2024, after all the grave violation took place in the presence of the authorities, finally efficacy was brought to life when the ICJ in accordance with article 96 of the Charter of the United Nations pursuant to Article 65 of the Statute of the Court rendered advisory opinion on the questions in issue. The court further dealt whether the questions so raised had any legal basis or not. After considering two questions-

- Whether legal consequences arise from certain practices and policies of Israel as an occupying power in the situation of belligerent occupation since 1967?
- How such practices and policies affect the legal status of occupation in the light of certain rules and principles of international law and as to the arising of legal consequences.

The court after dealing with these questions accepted that the request made as in accordance with the Charter of the Statue of Court, therefore having the jurisdiction in this matter. But in situations of belligerency like this ICJ was approached not to seek opinion on a matter which required its

assistance but rather seek the Court's confirmation of a particular legal conclusion relevant to the resolution of a bilateral dispute. Further in its Wall Advisory Opinion, the court didn't express viewers to the legal status of the Gaza Strip, though it being an integral part of the territory. On July 19, 2024, the International Court of Justice issued an advisory opinion, stating Israel's Occupation of the Palestinian territories unlawful and that the occupation violates international law and Israel must make reparations for the damages. This opinion was vehemently neglected by the Israelis.

Role of United Nations Organisation-

The United Nations is regarded as the international forum of resolving disputes between countries. Though in the recent past few months, it is all over the news that UN is trying to protect Palestinians from the clutches of the Israeli Occupation, the structural failure in the past cannot be overlooked or forgotten. Even after multiple votes by the Security Council and General Assembly on resolutions calling for ceasefire in Gaza, one of the big five permanent members, United States voted against 12 states to defeat the Council's resolution for the humanitarian pause. To sum up, the US has used its veto powers over 30 times to protect Israel against past UN action seeking to halt its aggression on Gaza. It has also prevented the Security Council from referring the case in this regard to the International Court of Justice. The UN could have utilized the Genocide Convention as the most relevant treaty to achieve the end of violence. In the final analysis, it appears on the face of it that US holds sway over the United Nations Organisations and all its actions are influenced by the US.

The scale of this diplomatic obstruction is borne out by the voting record. By November 2024, the United States had cast its forty-ninth veto against an Israel-related Security Council draft resolution, including multiple vetoes specifically blocking calls for a ceasefire in Gaza since October 2023. Meanwhile, the United Nations General Assembly, acting at its resumed Tenth Emergency Special Session, adopted resolutions demanding an immediate and unconditional ceasefire with overwhelming majorities of 153 to 10 in December 2023 and 158 to 9 in December 2024, demonstrating the near-universal character of global opinion in favour of the protection of

Palestinian civilians.⁸ The non-binding character of General Assembly resolutions has allowed the Security Council veto to remain the principal instrument of impunity, insulating Israel from any enforcement action under the United Nations Charter.

The seeds of success in a nation are best planted by its women and children but they themselves were buried in the soil, some even before making it in this world by the atrocities and sufferings put on them. The exploitation of women and children in this conflict constitutes a major part in itself and it cannot and should not be ever forgotten. Women, and children, are to be cherished and respected, not terrorized. The Muslim religion, be it of any sect or denomination, even in times of war in ancient times, used to spare their women and children considering them weak. The concept of equality stepped in and they are no longer considered weak but to focus on them largely in war crimes is rather a coward act to bring a nation down. Organisations that cater to women and children like Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) and United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) shall be responsible for the lifelong trauma caused to them, and shall answer for an entire generation lost to war.

The statistical evidence of harm to women and children in Gaza since October 2023 is stark and, by any measure, constitutes a humanitarian catastrophe of the gravest order. According to UN Women, more than 38,000 women and girls have been killed since the commencement of hostilities, with close to 11,000 sustaining injuries of sufficient severity to result in permanent disability, and nearly one million women and girls having been displaced. UNICEF has documented that, as of early 2026, at least 21,289 children have been reported killed in the Gaza

⁸ Middle East Eye, 'The 49 Times the US Used Veto Power Against UN Resolutions on Israel' (25 November 2024) <<https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/49-times-us-has-used-veto-power-against-un-resolutions-israel>> accessed 10 June 2025; UN News, 'UN General Assembly Votes Overwhelmingly to Demand a Humanitarian Ceasefire in Gaza' (12 December 2023) <<https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/12/1144717>> accessed 10 June 2025.

Strip, representing a proportion of child fatalities that has no parallel in any recent armed conflict.⁹ The failure of CEDAW, UNICEF, and the broader international protection system to prevent or halt this loss of life underlines the authors' central contention that the mechanisms of international humanitarian law remain largely performative in the absence of binding enforcement capacity.

Further, Israel's use of natural resources in the occupied Palestinian territory is inconsistent with its obligation under international law. Israel has exercised its regulatory authority as an occupied power in a manner that is **inconsistent with the rules reflected in Article 43 of the Hague Regulations and Article 64 of the fourth Geneva Convention**¹⁰.

The large-scale confiscation of lands in the provision of the access to natural resources has deprived the local population of their basic means of subsistence leading to their departure. Furthermore, a series of measures taken by the Israeli military forces has exacerbated the pressure on Palestinian Territory against their will. The policies and practices of the Israel in the occupied Palestinian territory are in complete breach of the prohibition of racial segregation and apartheid.

Chapter 5

DATA ANALYSIS

The information and data for this research topic has been collected and analyzed through books, articles and survey of a concerned mass taken forward by Qualitative Research through an online questionnaire form created via google so as to reach the audience from a distance.

⁹ UN Women, 'In Focus: Supporting Women and Girls Affected by the War on Gaza' (UN Women, 2025) <<https://www.unwomen.org/en/articles/in-focus/gaza>> accessed 10 June 2025; UNICEF, 'Unicef State of Palestine Humanitarian Situation Update' (UNICEF, 3 February 2026) <<https://www.unicef.org/sop/reports/unicef-state-palestine-humanitarian-situation-update>> accessed 10 June 2025.

¹⁰ ICRC, 'Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War of 12 August 1949, Article 64' <<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/gciv-1949/article-64>> accessed 24 December 2024.

Fig: Showing opinion on a scale of how far International law has been successful in protecting women and children.

Fig: Mixed response on whether humanitarian law has played its part effectively or not.

Chapter 6

COCLUSION AND WAY FORWARD.

The Israeli- Palestinian issue started off as a conflict which, with time, appears to be a multi-faceted humanitarian problem. The researcher has tried to analyse the situation, current social status, the role of international humanitarian actors in providing aid to the civilians and where they failed in their role. This research does not cover every aspect of relevant issue of the conflict rather it underscores and analyses several concerns relating to violation of International humanitarian Law.

The major concentration of this research was on reflecting the background and the role of international humanitarian law and its actors in protection of Palestinian civilians.

Suggestions-

- Codification of laws related to International Humanitarian nature and implementation of the same.
- Sanctions on the countries committing war crimes is the crying need of the hour.
- A global compensation fund, financed by member states, that would ensure timely redressal for victims of violation.
- Declarations related to human rights must be enforced by every country in their legal system and teaching the future generations so that they can raise their voice whenever atrocities occur.

The humanitarian law violation must be immediately monitored as well as documented. It is also critical to form a strong international framework. As law students, the researchers are of the view that there are enough well-defined conventions, regulations, rules and treaties. What is lacking is the execution of those. Along with the rules and conventions, the researcher believes that moral values and sensibility should be rooted in the minds of all. No party in an armed conflict shall be above international law is the goal that should be set up. As a researcher, we cannot change the world with the ideas in our mind, until it is documented for the world to see and know.

'It is not love or morality or international law that determines the outcome of world affairs, but the changing of distribution of organized force.'

-William Woodruff

Chapter 7

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